

Read and See: Dual Approaches to Content Representation in the Digital Edition Buber-Korrespondenzen Digital

In the course of the 24-year Buber-Korrespondenzen Digital project, the corpus of letters written and received by Martin Buber will be edited, numbering over 41,000. As one of the most influential Jewish philosophers and thinkers of the 20th century, Buber's extensive correspondence provides a unique insight into the intellectual, cultural and political networks of his era. The corpus, which spans 70 years of correspondence (1895-1965) with more than 7,000 correspondents from all over the world and encompasses 16 languages, presents significant editorial challenges. In order to manage this immense volume, the editorial team made two key decisions. Firstly, the decision was taken to concentrate on eight thematic modules reflecting the project's core research questions. Secondly, a decision was taken to implement a *modular edition* approach (Jurst-Görlach 2025:162-164), utilising a three-tier system of editorial depth:

- (i) letters of particular significance for the thematic modules receive full transcription, with extensive annotation and commentary;
- (ii) letters of moderate research interest are provided with content summaries and entity identification (persons, organisations, places, events, works mentioned, and keywords) to facilitate further research and reuse by third parties;
- (iii) all letters are documented with basic metadata, making them discoverable and available for future research and reuse.

This project constitutes the first comprehensive cataloguing of Buber's correspondence. The adoption of a *modular edition* approach has enabled a balance to be struck between scholarly rigour and the practical demands of editing such a vast corpus, making this multilingual correspondence accessible to researchers while maintaining high editorial standards in the areas that matter most. It is important to note that all correspondence (100%) receives a baseline level (iii) treatment, 65% additionally receives level (ii), and 25% receives the full treatment of levels (i), (ii), and (iii).

The project employs a dual "Read and See" approach to content representation at the intermediate tier (ii) of editorial depth. Initially, the entities referenced in the correspondence are systematically identified and catalogued. Subsequently, letters receive both a human-readable summary in plain language that concisely describes the essential content for researchers, and a machine-readable structured representation using entity-relation triples designed for computational analysis (Jurst-Görlach/Kollatz 2023). To illustrate this point, consider a contentious exchange between the correspondent and Buber regarding politics. The human-readable summary might describe this exchange narratively, while the machine-readable structured representation captures the same content as formalised triples such as "PersonA attacks PersonB" or "PersonA disagrees_with PersonB about Topic." The project

has developed its own vocabulary for these triples, which has proven particularly effective for capturing the types of relationships typical in correspondence.

Within the data model, these relationships are represented by the TEI element `<relation>`, for instance: `<relation active="PersonA" name="attacks" passive="PersonB"/>` (Jurst-Görlach 2024, and figure 3). Crucially, the entity-relation model is evidence-based and letter-centred: only relationships explicitly documented in each letter are captured as triples. The letter serves as the documentary evidence for each statement, rather than incorporating general world knowledge about the entities. This methodological approach ensures that each relationship is grounded in a specific historical source. In this regard, the project aligns with Georg Vogeler's concept of the *assertive edition*, which characterises editions that represent content as structured assertions or propositions derived from the source text (Vogeler 2019). By modelling relationships as evidence-based statements anchored in specific letters, the edition facilitates the kind of propositional access to historical information that assertive editions are designed to provide. For large-scale network analysis at the macro level across all correspondence, the project has explored the use of Neo4j graph database technology (figure 1), while Mermaid.js has proven highly effective for visualising the entity-relation model of individual letters at the micro level (figure 2). It is noteworthy that Mermaid.js employs a straightforward markdown-based syntax that is immediately comprehensible even to users with limited digital expertise, for example:

```
PersonA(labelA):::person --> |attacks| PersonB(labelB):::person
```

(figure 4). This accessibility renders the visualisation workflow transparent and reproducible, thus enabling editors to create and verify relationship diagrams without the necessity of specialised programming knowledge. This dual-layer abstraction—textual summary and visual/structural summary—serves complementary purposes: the narrative textual summary provides researchers with immediate comprehension of letter contents, while the triple-based visual representation enables computational analysis, network visualisation, and systematic querying of relational patterns across the entire corpus.

The combination of "Read and See" thus establishes a bridge between human reading and interpretation on the one hand, and digital humanities methods on the other. This renders Buber's correspondence accessible to both traditional scholarly interpretation and data-driven research approaches. This dual approach exemplifies how digital storytelling in digital scholarly editions can serve multiple narrative layers: preserving the human story of intellectual exchange while simultaneously creating new computational narratives that reveal patterns, networks, and relationships invisible in traditional narrative interpretation.

The project is funded by the Akademienprogramm, the joint research programme of the German academies of sciences. All research data are openly available in the project's repository at <https://gitlab.rlp.net/adwmainz/digicademy/bkd/correspondences>. Letters are also successively integrated into correspSearch (<https://correspsearch.net/en/home.html>), which enables searching and networking across numerous digital and printed letter editions. This

paper presents ongoing research from the Buber-Korrespondenzen Digital project, which is currently in its fifth year of a planned 24-year edition programme.

References

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Figures

Figure 1: Network visualization of entity relationships across four letters using Neo4j, demonstrating macro-level patterns in Buber's correspondence.

Theodor Herzl an Chaim Weizmann, 14. Mai 1903

file: [BKD02512.19030514.01.A.xml](#), [preview](#)

▼ content

- Herzl dankt Weizmann für dessen Ausführungen über die Lage in Russland sowie die Aktivitäten der Demokratischen Fraktion.
- Herzl lehnt Opposition nicht per se ab, kritisiert aber das Vorgehen der Demokratischen Fraktion in der Altneuland-Kontroverse scharf und rechnet mit dem Ausscheiden einiger ihrer Mitglieder aus der Zionistischen Bewegung.

- ▶ internalNote
- ▶ persons
- ▶ organizations
- ▶ places
- ▶ works
- ▶ events
- ▶ letters
- ▶ keywords
- ▼ Relationales Entitätenmodell

Figure 2: Entity-relation diagram of a single letter generated with Mermaid.js, illustrating the micro-level relationship structure.

```
<listRelation>
<relation active="P.0002131" name="attacks" passive="K.0000002"/>
<relation active="P.0002131" name="defends" passive="K.0000003"/>
<relation active="P.0005612" name="staysIn" passive="O.0000010" notAfter="1903-05-06"/>
<relation active="P.0002131" name="supporterOf" passive="P.0005612"/>
</listRelation>
```

Figure 3: Entity-relations of a single letter encoded in XML/TEI with element `<relation/>`.

```
<pre class="mermaid">
graph LR
P.0002131(Herzl, Theodor):::person --> |attacks| K.0000002(Demokratische
Fraktion):::organization
P.0002131(Herzl, Theodor):::person --> |defends| K.0000003(Aktionskomitee der Zionistischen
Bewegung):::organization
P.0005612(Weizmann, Chaim):::person --> |staysIn notAfter 1903-05-06|
O.0000010(Russland):::place
P.0002131(Herzl, Theodor):::person --> |supporterOf| P.0005612(Weizmann, Chaim):::person
classDef person fill:#e9c3b6
classDef organization fill:#E5C9D7
classDef place fill:#B7DDe9
</pre>
```

Figure 4: Entity-relations of a single letter transformed into mermaid.js markdown notation.

Abstract

The paper will present ongoing research from the long-term Buber-Korrespondenzen Digital project, which will edit over 41,000 letters by and to Martin Buber. To manage the huge volume of letters, a *modular edition* approach with three tiers of editorial depth is applied. The oral presentation will focus on the intermediate tier, where a dual "Read and See" methodology is implemented: letters receive both human-readable summaries in plain language and machine-readable structured representations using entity-relation triples. This evidence-based approach captures only relationships explicitly documented in each letter, aligning with Georg Vogeler's concept of the *assertive edition*. The project uses TEI <relation> elements to model relationships and employs Neo4j for macro-level network analysis and Mermaid.js for micro-level visualization of individual letters. This dual approach bridges traditional humanistic scholarship with digital humanities methods, exemplifying how narrative summaries and computational modeling can serve complementary purposes in digital scholarly editions.

Keywords

Digital Scholarly Edition

Assertive Edition

Entity Relation Model